

RESIDUAL CHARACTERISTIC OF BENDING MOMENT ON REPEATED FOLDING MOTION OF COATED PAPERBOARD CREASED BY ROUND-EDGE KNIFE

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1 Introduction

A wedge indentation processing is widely used for cutting off and creasing a complicated-formed pattern from a sheet material such as carton boxes, labels, insulation films and similar metal thin sheets [1-2]. If any cracks occur at the outside of folded parts of paperboard which made cabinet, the mechanical strength of the cabinet is weakened and also the folded parts are inferior in decorative aspects. A few reports for in-plane elongation of paperboard during indentation of creaser were shown by Halladay and Ulm [3]. Actual creasing range was investigated as the relationship between the crease depth and crease width by Hine [4].

Nagasawa *et al.* [5-7] reported about the folding stiffness with respect to the indentation depth of the creaser and also discussed with the crease deviation effect on the folding deformation characteristics. Here, the bending moment response with the folding motion was measured by using a bending-strength tester (BST-150M [8]). This testing device was evaluated by hand motion, and the relationship between bending moment and rotation angle was only one time investigated for each specimen. The correlation between the bending strength (resistance) and several primary problems on actual processing phenomenon was not sufficiently discussed in the past. To know the reaction force acting on a hinge, which is fold with a creased line, it is important to adjust the mechanical condition in the boxing stage by automatic folder gluer machine.

However, it is difficult to estimate the correlation from the initial strength of creased part, such as the maximum bending moment and the initial gradient of bending moment which are evaluated by one way motion. Furthermore, as the transient deformation of creased part subjected to the bending moment was

not observed by any camera during the bending test, the relationship between de-lamination and reduction of bending stiffness could not be verified in direct when the initial indentation depth of creasing rule was varied.

In this study, therefore, a new prototype testing apparatus has been developed for seeking the bending moment and the side view picture of creased part during repeated folding motion. In order to reveal the hysteresis characteristics of bending resistance during the repeated folding motion from the initial position up to 60 degree, and also to investigate the residual behavior of bending moment, a white-coated paperboard of 0.3 /mm thickness was scored with a round-edge knife (creasing rule) and a grooved counter plate under a specified feed velocity, and then the repeated bending test was carried out by varying the tracking angle.

2 Experimental condition and method

2.1 Pre-processing of specimen

Fig. 1 illustrates experimental apparatus in making the test pieces of paperboard scored by a round-edge knife with radius of $r=0.45$ /mm and the face plate with the groove width of $B=1.3$ /mm. The creaser direction angle ϕ was chosen as 90° [7]. The nominal shear strains $\gamma=2d/B$ were chosen as 0.0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 [5-6], while the feed velocity was chosen as $V=0.0167$ /mms⁻¹. Where, d is the indentation depth of creasing rule to paperboard. Any rubber fixtures were not implemented here.

The test pieces were prepared as 10 pieces of the rectangle-formed white-coated paperboard (the basis weight $\rho=228\sim 237$ /gm²), which had width of 40 /mm, length of 60 /mm, and thickness of 0.3 (0.297 \sim 0.303) /mm, for each condition of chosen nominal

shear strain. The in-plane tensile test properties in machine direction (MD), based on JIS-P8113 (gauge length: 180 /mm, width: 15 /mm, feed velocity: $V=0.33$ / mms^{-1}), were as shown in **Table 1**. All paper boards were kept in a room which had the temperature of 296 /K and the humidity of 50 %RH.

Fig.1 Experimental apparatus for scoring

Table 1 In-plane tensile properties of white-coated paperboard in machine direction

Ultimate TS σ_B /MPa	41.1(40.2~42.7)
Proof S. 0.2%strain /MPa	11.1 (11.4~10.9)
Breaking true strain ϵ_B /%	1.71 (1.81~ 1.62)
Young's mod. E /GPa	5.72(5.91~5.53)

Fig.2 Bending test apparatus

2.2 Measurement of bending moment during repeated folding motion

Fig. 2 shows a schematic diagram and a general view of experimental apparatus for repeated folding motion test. **Fig. 3** is an example of relationship between folding angle θ and bending line moment

(resistance for the unit width) M . The sampling time of M , θ was chosen as 2 /ms.

Fig.3 Analysis parameters on folding resistance diagram (in case of $\gamma=0.4$, $\omega=0.2$ /rps)

Since the paperboard has viscous elasticity and creep characteristics during the folding process, rotation velocity of fixture ω was set to 0.2 /rps and stopping time for returning back was set to zero at a tracking position of Θ and a second starting position of θ_2' . The tracking angle (position) Θ was varied from 0 up to 60 /°. As the accelerated duration (transient time) was set to 0.1 /s for each starting/stopping, the rotation velocity ω reached to 0.2 /rps for $\Theta > 7.2$ /°. In case of $\Theta = 10$ /°, it is estimated that the stationary state of $\omega = 0.2$ /rps is kept for 2.8 /° (28%).

The initial (first term) gradient of bending line moment C_1 ($=G_1$) [5], the second term gradient C_2 , the released angle of θ_2 and the area of closed curve A_{CC} were investigated with respect to γ .

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Permanent deformation

Fig. 4 shows a representative example of the relationship between bending line moment M and folding angle θ (up to tracking angle Θ) by varying the nominal shear strain γ . The first starting position of θ_1 was varied with γ , while the second starting position of θ_2 was varied with tracking angle Θ .

Fig. 5 shows the angle of starting position θ_1 which corresponds to the residual camber derived from blade indentation without rubberring.

Fig. 6 shows the released angle θ_2 with the tracking angle Θ by varying the nominal shear strain γ .

Fig.4 Relationship between bending line moment and rotation angle by varying nominal shear strain, in case of tracking angle of 60 /°.

Fig.5 Relationship between angle of starting position and nominal shear strain (indentation depth of blade)

Fig.6 Dependency of released angle on tracking angle by varying nominal shear strain

Eq. (1) shows an approximation of θ_1 with γ , while Eq. (2) is an approximation of θ_2 with γ and Θ , respectively.

$$\theta_1 = -8.50\gamma^2 - 2.84\gamma \quad (0 < \gamma < 1) \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_2 = a_1\Theta + a_0 \quad (0 < \Theta < 60 /^\circ) \quad (2)$$

$$a_1 = 0.434\gamma^2 - 0.533\gamma + 0.75 \quad (0 < \gamma < 1)$$

$$a_0 = -9.492\gamma^2 + 11.32\gamma - 7.742$$

It was found that θ_2 was linearly varied with Θ and about a half of Θ for $60^\circ > \Theta > 30^\circ$, it was less than 1.5° for $\Theta < 10^\circ$. Namely, when Θ was less than 10° , the permanent deformation of angle was remarkably small.

Fig.7 Relationship between bending line moment and rotation angle by varying tracking angle, in case of nominal shear strain of $\gamma=0.4$

3.2 Relationship between second term hysteresis area and first peak point of bending moment

Fig. 7 shows examples of the relationship between bending line moment M and folding angle θ by varying tracking angle Θ for nominal shear strain of $\gamma=0.4$, rotation speed of $\omega=0.2$ / rps. From this response, the integration of closed curve A_{CC} (hysteresis area for the second term loop) was calculated using the trapezoidal method. **Fig. 8** shows A_{CC} with respect to Θ by varying γ .

From Fig.4 and Fig.8, following features were detected: (1) When $\gamma > 0.6$, the overshoot of M disappeared and A_{CC} was almost linear with Θ ; (2) the peak position (angle) θ_{1p} of overshoot of M appeared to match with transition limit Θ_T of gradient of A_{CC} ($\partial A_{CC} / \partial \Theta$); For an example, when

$\gamma=0.2$, $\theta_{1p} \approx 20^\circ$ and it corresponds to the transition limit Θ_T of $\partial A_{CC} / \partial \Theta$.

Fig.8 Relationship between 2nd term hysteresis area and tracking angle

Fig.9 CCD Side views of scored paperboard during folding process in case of $\phi=90^\circ$, $\gamma=0.2$

Fig.10 Transition model of creasing process

Fig. 9 shows CCD photographs of side views of scored paperboard during the bending test. In this picture, a case of $\gamma=0.2$ was shown. From Fig.9 (b), the initial damage of score and the shallow buckling

were detected, while the bulging was promoted with the scored corners (nodes) in Fig.9 (c), (d).

The transition model was illustrated in **Fig.10** in order to exaggerate the transition of creasing process. At the peak position of overshoot, since a certain level of long-parallel de-laminations occur in the scored zone, the in-plane bending stiffness is remarkably decreased and then it appears that variance of hysteresis area increases in this process. When the folding angle θ passes through the peak point θ_{1p} of overshoot, the inner bulging is promoted (increased) but the deformation of de-laminated zone is restricted with the immobile nodes as shown in Fig.10 (b).

So far, it is revealed that the creasing deformation at the peak point of overshooting is different from that after passing through the peak point of overshooting. The gradient $\partial A_{CC} / \partial \Theta$ in the range of pre-stage of overshooting ($\theta < \theta_{1p}$) tends to be larger than that for the post-stage of overshooting ($\theta > \theta_{1p}$). When the inner de-lamination of scored paperboard is insufficient by the specified γ , A_{CC} remarkably increased in the pre-stage and the peak of overshooting.

Fig.11 Angles of peak position and transition limit (representative examples)

Fig. 11 shows the representative examples of angle of the peak position θ_{1p} and angle of the transition limit Θ_T , which were derived from Fig.4 and Fig.8. From this graph, it is confirmed that θ_{1p} is approximately equal to Θ_T .

3.3 Gradient of line moment with folding angle as stiffness

Regarding the material properties of coated paperboard, the first peak of bending line moment M_{p1} and the first term gradient of bending line moment C_1 are fundamental properties when nominal shear strain is zero. Comparing the current paperboard shown in Table 1 with referred specimen of C [6], the thickness and the basis weight are fairly different with each other. In order to know the stiffness per unit thickness of those specimens, M_{p1} was normalized as $M_{p1} \cdot t^{-2}$ and C_1 was also normalized as $C_1 \cdot t^{-2}$.

Table 2 Normalized peak bending moment and first gradient of paperboard w/o scoring

	UT Stress σ_B /MPa	Thickness t /mm	N.Peak M. $M_{p1} t^{-2}$ /MPa	N.F.Gradi. $C_1 t^{-2}$ /MPa.deg ⁻¹
Current specimen	41.1	0.30	6.33	0.61
Referred specimen	45.8	0.46	8.03	0.47

Fig.12 Dependency of first gradient of bending line moment on nominal shear strain

The calculated values were shown in Table 2. From this result, the current specimen has a little higher stiffness while the breaking strength is a little smaller.

Fig. 12 shows the first term gradient $C_1 = \partial M / \partial \theta|_{\theta=\theta_1}$ with respect to γ . The first term gradient C_1 /Ndeg⁻¹ was approximated with 2nd order power rule for $0 < \gamma < 0.6$, and approximated with a linear rule for $0.6 < \gamma < 1.0$ as shown in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4), respectively.

$$100C_1 = -6.3\gamma^2 - 2.3\gamma + 5.5 \quad (0 < \gamma < 0.6) \quad (3)$$

$$100C_1 = -2.8\gamma + 3.7 \quad (0.6 < \gamma < 1.0) \quad (4)$$

It is found that C_1 is remarkably decreased up to the limit condition ($\gamma \approx 0.6$) of disappearance of overshoot response of bending line moment, while it is linearly varied with γ after passing through the limit condition of disappearance ($\gamma > 0.6$).

Fig.13 Relationship between second gradient of bending line moment and tracking angle

Fig. 13 shows the second term gradient C_2 with respect to tracking angle θ , where γ was varied from 0.0 to 1.0. From this graph, followings are revealed: (1) C_2 is decreased with θ . It appears linearly with θ^{-1} for $\gamma < 0.6$; (2) C_2 is decreased and almost linear with γ for $\gamma < 0.6$ under keeping θ constant; (3) When $\gamma > 0.6$, C_2 is not so large in the range of $\theta = 10 \sim 30$ /°, while C_2 is remarkably large in the same range for $\gamma < 0.6$. This variance appears from the mechanism of Fig.10 (a). (4) The stiffness ratio of C_2/C_1 was 0.6~1.1 for $\theta < 20$ /°, while it was 0.4~0.6 in case of $40 > \theta > 60$ /°. To be less than 1.0 is equivalent to reduce the elastic bending stiffness of crease.

It is found that C_2/C_1 is roughly reduced to a half of virgin state for $\theta > 40$ /°. This reduction of C_2/C_1 seems to depend on the structural-material properties such as de-lamination resistance, inner friction characteristic. In order to decide the required stiffness of C_2 at a specified tracking angle, the nominal shear strain γ must be chosen appropriately from the aspect of production design needs.

3.4 Relationship between variance of A_{CC} and C_1

Assuming that the area of closed curve A_{CC} is linearly approximated with θ by using Eq. (5), coefficients a_{k1} and a_{k0} were estimated from Fig.8.

Here, the range of Θ was considered as $\Theta_T < \Theta < 60^\circ$.

$$A_{CC} = a_{k1}\Theta + a_{k0} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 14 (a) shows the coefficients of a_{k1} , a_{k0} with respect to γ , while Fig.14 (b) shows relationship between a_{k1} and C_1 . It is revealed that the intercept of a_{k0} is positive when the first peak of bending line moment appeared for $\gamma < 0.6$. Observing the correlation between a_{k1} and C_1 , they have the similar tendency with respect to γ , and following expression (6) is derived:

$$a_{k1} = 0.41 C_1 + 0.024 \quad (6)$$

It was found that a_{k1} had strongly related to C_1 when γ was varied.

(a) Coefficients a_{k0} , a_{k1} of A_{CC} expressed with Eq.(5)

(b) Relationship between a_{k1} and C_1

Fig.14 Dependency of A_{CC} on γ and C_1 for $\Theta_T < \Theta < 60^\circ$ (after passing through the peak point)

4 Conclusions

Twice-repeated bending characteristic of creased white-coated paperboard of 0.3 /mm thickness was investigated by varying nominal shear strain γ and tracking angle Θ , using a prototype crease strength tester under rotation angle velocity of 0.2 /rps. The obtained results were as follows:

- (1) The first term gradient C_1 was characterized with γ , while the second term gradient C_2 was characterized with γ and the inverse of tracking angle Θ^{-1} .
- (2) The first term starting position (angle) θ_1 was approximately expressed with second order power rule of γ , while the second term starting position (angle) θ_2 was expressed with the first order of Θ and the second order power rule of γ .
- (3) By introducing the area of closed curve of second term hysteresis A_{CC} , it is revealed that the gradient $\partial A_{CC} / \partial \Theta$ was remarkably varied with Θ when the creasing characteristics (the bending line moment and deformation of inner layers) of paper board was varied.
- (4) When the first term peak point of bending line moment appears for $\gamma < 0.6$, (i) many parallel de-laminations occur at the scored zone for $\theta < \theta_{1p}$, while (ii) a bulging of inner layers and rotary opening of de-laminated zone appear at two immobile nodes for $\theta > \theta_{1p}$. Where, θ_{1p} is the rotation angle of the first term peak point. Namely, it is revealed that there is a transition state from (i) to (ii) at near the first term peak point. Near the peak position, it was found that the gradient $\partial A_{CC} / \partial \Theta$ is remarkably varied with Θ .
- (5) It is confirmed that the developed measurement system is useful for detecting the relationship between the second term hysteresis area and the bending stiffness parameters.

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